

THE INFLUENCE OF ANEMIA IN PREGNANT WOMEN ON THE INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF NEWBORNS WITH INTRAUTERINE HYPOTROPHY

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Abstract: Insufficient iron can cause the development of iron deficiency anemia during pregnancy. A negative consequence of prolonged iron deficiency anemia is oxygen starvation of the baby. For the mother, anemia can cause early toxicosis or severe gestosis, the appearance of which only increases fetal hypoxia. Iron deficiency can also cause premature birth. The risk of complications during childbirth also increases. Women in labor with anemia often experience weak labor and bleeding during and/or after childbirth, especially during cesarean section. In addition, a lack of iron in the body of a pregnant woman can cause the development of anemia in the child after birth.

Keywords: pregnant woman, anemia, cesarean section, premature birth, intrauterine malnutrition.

Relevance: Anemia during pregnancy is so common that for many years a decrease in hemoglobin levels during this period to 100 g/l (61%) was considered normal physiological process. When it became known that during pregnancy the volume of circulating blood increases by approximately 30% or more, a phrase like “physiological hydremia” became fashionable. However, it has often been noted that some women, especially those with high social status and peak fertility, do not experience such “physiological” changes. With the accumulation of knowledge about iron metabolism and a better understanding of the importance of iron balance in pregnant women and non-pregnant women, it became obvious that most cases of anemia are caused by iron deficiency and that there is no specific “anemia of pregnancy”.

The purpose of the study: was to study the effect of anemia in pregnant women of varying severity on indicators of physical development of newborns born with intrauterine malnutrition of varying degrees, occurring against the background of perinatal damage to the central nervous system

Materials and methods: A total of 152 newborns were examined, of which 106 newborns with various degrees of lesions of the central nervous system against the background of intrauterine malnutrition, 24 newborns with varying degrees of intrauterine malnutrition and 22 healthy newborns.

This work was carried out on the basis of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Clinic No. 1 of the Samarkand Medical University. The study of physical indicators by gender (in boys and girls) depending on the pathology in the mother confirmed not only the pattern of severity of intrauterine malnutrition, but also its dependence on the conditions of intrauterine development - the severity of the pathology in the mother.

Thus, with a mild degree of anemia in pregnant women, the weight and height deficit in newborn boys with varying degrees of perinatal damage to the central nervous system with a mild degree of intrauterine malnutrition compared with children in the control group was equal to 308 g and height - 1.3 cm; in girls - 445 g and height 1.6 cm.

With an average degree of anemia in pregnant women, the birth weight deficit in boys was already 547 g and height 1.8 cm; girls have a weight deficit of 658 g and a height of 2.3 cm, and severe anemia during pregnancy; boys have a weight deficit of 1025 g and a height of 3.6 cm; girls: weight 1059 g, height 3.3 cm

With only late toxicosis of pregnancy, newborns were born with intrauterine malnutrition and a deficit in weight and height (compared to children in the control group), corresponding to the degree of intrauterine malnutrition - mild , moderate and severe. When studying and assessing the functional state of systems and organs in newborns with intrauterine malnutrition, we used general clinical research methods.

On examination, a full-term newborn with intrauterine malnutrition is significantly different from a newborn born with normal weight.

The external signs of a newborn with intrauterine hypotrophy are quite characteristic: a sharp thinning or complete absence of the subcutaneous fat layer in all parts of the body except the face; disproportionate physique: relatively large head with a predominance of the cerebral skull over the facial one, pliability of the skull bones, open sutures and small fontanelle, relatively short legs and neck, low navel. The skin is brick-red in color with an abundance of wrinkles (the child has an senile appearance), an abundance of fluff (lanugo) on the face and throughout the body. In addition, the softness of the ears and their closeness to the head are typical; moderate or severe exophthalmos; undescended testicles into the scrotum in boys and underdevelopment of the labia majora in girls; swelling in the lower abdomen; lethargy, lack of movement. In 77 newborns, evidence of disembryogenesis was noted : Mongoloid eye shape

in 14 newborns, low eyelids in 26, heterochromia of the iris in 4, different-sized ears in 11 newborns, short frenulum of the tongue in 33 newborns, excessive folds on the neck in 38 newborns, pigeon chest in 4 newborns, a large distance between the nipples in 17, low navel in 21, hernias in 21, cryptorchidism in 12 newborns, underdevelopment of the labia in 18, large birthmarks with hair in 4 newborns, depigmented spots in 2 newborns. Availability of more than 5-6 dysembryogenetic stigmas are an indicator of an increased risk of delayed psychomotor development.

Conclusion: According to conducted research a significant deficit in weight and height in newborns (especially in female newborns) born to mothers with early and late toxicosis of pregnancy against the background of extragenital diseases should be explained primarily not only by the severity of the combined pathology, but also by insufficient treatment in antenatal clinics for early toxicosis in pregnant women with extragenital diseases.

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